

SUPPLEMENTARY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PARTICIPANTS

General Information
Participant Full Name:
Participant Code:
Sampling Date:
Sampling Time:
Location:

The URBANOME project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 945391.

BIOLOGICAL SAMPLE COLLECTION

1. When and what was your last meal before blood sampling? (Small meals such as fruit should also be reported.)

Date:

Time:

Meal:

2. On what date and time was the urine sample collected at your home?

Date:

Time:

3. Was it the first morning urine? Yes No

When and what was your last meal before urine sampling?

Date:

Time:

Meal:

4. Did you brush your teeth less than 30 minutes before saliva collection? Yes No

5. Did you consume any food or drink less than 30 minutes before saliva collection? Yes No

HOME – RESIDENTIAL ENVIRONMENT

1. Is any of the following facilities located within 300 meters of your residence?

	Yes	No	Do not know
1. Waste incineration plant			
2. Waste disposal area (all types of waste / hazardous or chemical waste)			
3. Gas station			
4. Mine			
5. Scrap yard			
6. Site where solvents are used (e.g., paint factory)			
7. Agricultural land or vineyard			
8. Printing facility			
9. Dry-cleaning service			
10. Car repair workshop			
11. Carpentry workshop			
12. Glass processing or production factory			
13. Steel plant			
14. Tannery			
15. Construction site			
16. Recycling facility			
17. Cement, pesticide, or plastic production plant			
18. Fertilizer production or composting facility (including sewage sludge treatment)			
19. Coal, oil, wood, or other power plant			
20. Metallurgical facility			
21. Factory producing or using adhesives			
22. Factory producing computers and/or electronic devices			
23. Factory producing photovoltaic products or solar water heaters			
24. Site producing or using epoxy resins			
25. Site producing or using filters			
26. Factory producing plastic or other food/beverage packaging			
27. Medical equipment production plant			
28. Plastic production factory			
29. Thermal paper production factory			
30. Battery/candle production plant			
31. Other industrial facility Please specify			

2. Have you noticed any of the following problems in your home recently?

Problems in your home	Yes	No	Do not know
1. Mold on walls or other surfaces			
2. Water leakage (e.g., broken pipes, roof leak, flooding)			
3. Mold odor			
4. Peeling paint on walls or windows			
5. Black dust			

3. Number of rooms in your home (excluding bathrooms and storage rooms):

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4. Monthly household income category:

1. Low income (<1500 €)
2. Middle income (1501–4000 €)
3. High income (>4001 €)

ACTIVITIES – NON-OCCUPATIONAL EXPOSURE

1. When did you perform the following activities before biological sampling?

Activities include:	Never	<12 hours	12–24 hours	24–48 hours	>48 hours	Do not know
Home repairs/construction						
Gardening						
Metal handling (e.g., welding, jewelry making)						
Use of dyes and inks (hair dye, textile dye, tattoo ink, printing)						
Use of pesticides						

PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS

1. When did you use the following before biological sampling?

Προϊόντα	Never	<12 hours	12–24 hours	24–48 hours	>48 hours	Do not know
Cosmetics (make-up, nail polish)						
Hair care products (spray, dye, beard products)						
Body care products (lotion, perfume, shower gel, deodorant)						
Sunscreen						

OCCUPATIONAL EXPOSURE

1. How many hours per day do you stay at your workplace?

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